

Sharing data in real-life situations

Denmark as example of collaboration across sectors

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Main challenges

The sharing of data is not explicitly regulated

- Public health and food health authorities
 - Afraid of sharing “too much” (potentially sensitive information can be found in genome sequences)
 - Prefer to retain control over information
- Same for companies
- Stronger protection of personal data (GDPR)
- Cross-border collaboration is challenging

The Danish food safety system - Overview

- The **risk management** is located in the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA)
- The **scientific risk assessment** and the **research-based assessment of monitoring data** are located at The National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (DTU Food)

Agreements

- ✓ Framework agreement with Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (*Rammeaftale 2021-2024*)
- ✓ Service agreement with DVFA (*Ydelsesaftale 2021-2024*)
- DTU Food provides consulting to the DVFA in particular within the following area:
Microbiological food safety, including zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance

Sharing data regarding outbreaks

National outbreaks of zoonotic gastrointestinal infections are investigated in collaboration among:

- Statens Serum Institut (SSI)
- DTU Food
- DVFA

Representatives from these institutions meet regularly in the **Central Outbreak Management Group** to discuss surveillance results, compare the reported occurrence of zoonotic agents in animals, food and feedstuffs with that in humans, and coordinate the investigation of outbreaks

Central Outbreak Management Group

Figure 8.1. Overview of the monitoring and outbreak investigation network for reporting infectious pathogens in humans, animals, foodstuffs and feedstuffs in Denmark, 2020

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 1/6

An increased number of human cases of a listeriosis is observed. Sequencing of the isolates from the human cases shows that the isolates are indistinguishable, thus a common source is suspected

DATA: Isolates, genome sequences of such isolates.

Collected by **physicians**, who send specimens from suspected cases to one of the clinical microbiology laboratories

The **clinical microbiology laboratory** reports to SSI directly
SSI performs the whole-genome sequencing

SHARED

WITH: Can be occasionally shared with university

HOW (legal tools):

1. Material Transfer Agreement
2. Personal data requires separate documents

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 2/6

The outbreak is investigated by the Central Outbreak Management Group.

The COMG has the task to make a hypothesis (e.g. that the infection was caused by a specific product, which is prepared at a certain food company).

The hypothesis is first of all tested with **analytical epidemiology (interviews)**.

DATA: Interviews with patients

COLLECTED BY: SSI

SHARED

WITH: Central Outbreak Management Group

HOW: Personal data remains under the control of SSI (no transfer) and are only used by the Group for the specific purpose of making the hypothesis.

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 3/6

From interviews with the latest cases, it is clear that the persons infected had used the same greengrocer's and had eaten the same type of product prepared there.

The hypothesis must also be based on **microbiological laboratory results and trace-back of food.**

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 4/6

Case 1)

Upon recommendation from the Central Outbreak Management Group, or upon own initiative', DVFA's personnel perform a **control visit** to the company and listeria is detected in the food and production environment.

DATA: Isolates from the production environment, genome sequences of such isolates.

COLLECTED AND SEQUENCED BY: DVFA

SHARED

WITH: Can be share with university

HOW (legal tools):

1. Material Transfer Agreement
2. Declaration on transfer for research purposes in case of personal data included

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 5/6

Case 2)

The food industry has a **HACCP based programme** in which sampling for listeria monocytogenes is included. A subset of the isolates is stored at the contracted laboratory.

DATA: Isolates from the production environment, genome sequences of such isolates

COLLECTED BY: Company; sequencing made privately in an authorized laboratory.

SHARED

WITH: DVFA

HOW: typically, only results of the analysis (company has duty to report to DVFA in case of suspect, but not an obligation to share all data).

Data sharing scenario – Listeria outbreak 6/6

The sequences from the listeria isolates of the patients and from the food and production environment were genetically closely related.

The company is ordered to **discontinue production in accordance with an injunction** issued by the DVFA

Conclusions: Sharing of data with the university

From: **DVFA**

Which data: **Data from food related to bacteria** (samples collected by DVFA or sent to DVFA by a company which has a surveillance program; isolates – genome sequences – metadata)

Transfer of isolates/genome sequences to the university requires a **Material Transfer Agreement**

Challenges in data sharing:

- Use for research purposes requires specific permission. Typically projects where the DVFA is involved
- Confidentiality. It may not be allowed to make public sequencing data on samples not collected by DVFA but by the company
- Lack of metadata may lead to missing information (e.g., lack of reference material)
- Metadata such as data on sole proprietorship / farmers (family business) is considered personal data, which requires further consideration and compliance with data privacy rules

Conclusions: Sharing of data with the university

From: **SSI**

Which data: **Data on humans/patients** (isolates and metadata, data included in interviews)

- ✓ Sharing of patients' personal data is subject to **data privacy legislation** (GDPR and national legislation)

Depending on role (controller / processor), different legal documentation is needed: either data processing agreement or declaration/agreement on transfer of personal data for further processing for research purposes

- ✓ Transfer of biological material for research purposes requires a **Material Transfer Agreement**. Typically, when the public authority shares a common interest in publication of results. Only minimum metadata is shared.

Thank you